

1 Transcript

2 **Eleni Maria Kalafati**

3 **05.06.2025, Sorbonne**

4 Transcript by FN

5 **FN:** Yeah, I'm trying to make it a conversation, that's my aim, at least for
6 here. And maybe just to come back to it, journal is diamond open access,
7 and the idea to support young academics on their way. Maybe to just sort
8 of,

8 can you give me a short explanation of what you do and how it actually
9 connects to negotiations?

10 **EMK:** So, my initial field of study was economics, but my department was
11 international and European economic studies. So, apart from the traditional
12 economic courses like microeconomics, macroeconomics, econometrics,
13 and
14 boring things like that, math, and statistics, we also had courses on
15 European Union, law, international organizations, so I was more in touch
16 with the holistic perspective of the international economic relations.
17 After that, I worked for many different organizations in the private sector,
18 in the public sector, trying to figure out what I would like to do with
19 such a degree. There are not many options in Greece. I've always wanted to
20 be a diplomat. I did my internship at the Hellenic Ministry of Foreign
21 Affairs. I was fascinated by the way things work. This is where I saw
22 negotiations in action for the very first time, and it was like a virus. I
23 caught it, and I never gained back my health. So, I was trying to see what
24 I can do with that.

24 By the time, it was 2018, when I saw that my department, the one that I
25 have studied, starts a new master's degree. It's a Master of Sciences in
26 International Negotiations. I said, okay, let's go. It was founded in 2018,
27 the very first series of graduates we were admitted in 2019. So, I was the
28 very first one, actually, to make an application and the very first one to
29 pass the interview. And I've ended up the valedictorian of the department
30 for the master's degree for that year. It was everything I expected. We've
31 combined the methodology of the science with the negotiations, giving
32 something completely different to what negotiation was thought to be. And
33 that gave me access, not only to politics, but also to business
34 negotiations. I've tried to work in that field, but education is what
35 caught my eye and my heart.

36 So, I was engaged in corporate training at first, and then I was offered a
37 place at a private college in Greece, where I taught students basic
38 economics for business, but a set of other courses for soft skills
39 development, negotiations among them. It was on the syllabus, that's why
40 they gave these courses to me. And then my entire life, like from 2019,
41 2020, until now, my entire life is around negotiations, no matter what is
42 the type. I consult businesses, I train businesses, I consult politicians.
43 But to educate the younger generation, to get the culture of negotiations,
44 not only the techniques and the practices, but actually the culture of
45 conflict resolution, how you can sit down, let the dialogue flow, talk

46 about interests, and find a mutually beneficial solution. So, my entire
47 life is negotiations. The past five years, yes, there is not a single day
48 that passes that I am not negotiating.

49 **FN:** How do you see a difference between the culture of negotiation, as you
50 call it, between politicians and businesses?

51 **EMK:** Well, I know that a lot of businesses, a lot of scholars in this field
52 believe that they are actually the same. For me, having done both, they
53 have the same principles, the same techniques, but in businesses, you end
54 up talking about numbers. Like, after everything, after all the trust
55 building and the long-term relationships, in the end, it's all about the
56 money. At least in Greece. Okay, I can talk about my country, where I've
57 consulted the majority. But in politics, even if it's something, for
58 example, an agreement that it is beneficial for everybody, there comes a
59 legislation, for example, to support families that they live under poverty.
60 There is not a single person that personally disagrees with the content of
61 that legislation. So, basically, to form a legislation, you go through the
62 committees and then to plenary sessions. It is a negotiation, and it is a
63 multi-level negotiation.

64 A political party, for example, not even a political party, let's downsize
65 it even more. One politician, they need to be aligned with what they
66 believe, but at the same time, they need to have good relationships with
67 the political party they are part of, because they get things from it. It's
68 a give-and-take relationship both ways. But at the same time, there are the
69 voters that they influence the entire process, because some of the voters
70 will not want for one political party to vote a proposal of another
71 political party. You understand how this works. So, even if it is, for
72 example, measures for poor families, for children, for well-being, just
73 because a politician disagrees with the government, they will say no and
74 become an obstacle into that. The way politics work, at least in my country,
75 Greece, it's that the ones that they do have the majority of the votes,
76 the majority of the seats in the parliament, they can pass the legislation.
77 So, no matter what you do, you can express your disagreement with
something.

78 Still, it passes, because the majority votes for that.

79 But there is more sensitive stuff that, even within the government, you
80 cannot find consensus. For example, the Greek-Turkish relationships. This
81 is something that creates huge problems on how to build a consensus
within

82 the same party. So, it is a constant fight for building consensus.

83 Something that in business negotiations, you do not find. And imagine how
84 that government has to go to the EU, and there is an agreement in the EU,
85 for example, in the EU directive, that it is compliant for the member
86 states, but when it comes through the parliament to get it legalized as
87 part of the national legal framework, you find block walls everywhere. I
88 don't know if it is the same in every country, because every country has
89 different legislation systems, but I've seen that in politics a lot. No
90 matter the political party, I've seen that from the far right to the far
91 left, that it is hard to build the cooperation that we see in business.

92 In the business. If something is good, it will be voted, in quotation marks.

93 They will do it. They will agree. We've seen tough situations handled
94 beautifully, for example, in mergers and acquisitions. Two businesses

merge,
95 and they find that there is an excess of human resources, so some people
96 need to be let off. This is a very sensitive topic. But we see that in the
97 negotiations for this M&A, both businesses are actually on the same page.
98 What can we do to make our employees better off? Even if we have to let
99 them go, we need to do it in a way that we respect their rights, and we
100 respect their value that it was brought to either business. From the time
101 they sit on the table for the merger, it is our people. Something you do
102 not see in politics.

103 **FN:** That's a fascinating point. Also, regarding the consensus building,
104 where you have the problem in the party, between the parties and the
105 government.

106 **EMK:** And then the government with the foreign obligations. So, it's a
107 multi-level. Like you have a two-level game, three-level game. These are
108 four-level games. It expands. It becomes more complicated.

109 **FN:** Fascinating. I have a lot of thoughts to that.

110 **EMK:** We can discuss with this for a very long time. If I start talking
111 about that, for example, political parties tend to be under the European
112 political umbrella, several other parties, and they have to negotiate again
113 with them on what is accepted and what is not accepted. So, if you play
114 ball in two courts at the same time, imagine that you have a third court
115 called citizens and voters. They can lift you up. They can destroy you.

116 **FN:** And I like the point of the sensitive topics and how they are handled
117 in these two different spheres. If we take a look at the European Union at
118 the moment, I have the feeling we have quite some sensitive topics from
119 political shifts, social migration, finances, climate, power structures.
120 There is this kind of disagreement or differences that we have in the
121 European Union. What is your perspective? Which of these shifts influences
122 the way we negotiate in Europe at the moment the most?

123 **EMK:** Well, in Europe, we see that immigration actually created several
124 problems. Even people that they didn't have a problem with immigrants
125 before, after 2010, 2012, 2015, they are opposing this. It's like we
126 shifted from being humanitarian to being actually misanthropic. And when
we

127 are discussing, I'm talking about a very sensitive issue that in my country
128 is quite a topic. We see far-right political parties rise and they take
129 seats. And not all of them are nationalists. Some are very extreme. We have
130 seen these voices. We have heard these voices in every single country of
131 the EU. In Greece, we had a huge problem with the Golden Dawn, if you
have

132 heard, with pogroms against people that they have come here for a better
133 future. It is all a matter of how you see things. And I believe that after
134 multiple crises, people have not the faith needed in institutions,
135 especially the EU.

136 The way they handled the financial crisis and then the pandemic and the
137 immigration, they are all combined. And now we have the environmental
138 discussions to talk about. Like after a financial crisis and then the
139 pandemic that created financial problems, we have new regulations about
the

..2.1. European

..1.2. Social

..1.2. Social

..1.2. Social

..1.2. Social

140 ESG framework, the CSRD. And we see again countries rising up. We have
141 the
142 omnibus talks, the omnibus initiative, that they actually, it's a step back
143 from the CSRD as it was supposed to implement it because they weren't
144 engaged in the negotiations in the first place. But if you ask a common
145 person, like a person on the road who is a voter, who does have the same
146 rights as everybody else, what do you think about the environment? You
147 might hear one myth after the other, one, these theories that they're so
148 extreme. So when this is the climate in the general public, how do you
believe affects what is happening at a higher level?

..1.2. Social

149 **FN:** So, there is also the misinformation that you have to deal with?

..5.1. Essential Skill:

..2.1. European

150 **EMK:** It's a matter of education. People have shifted away from... And I see
151 that a lot in younger generations, unfortunately. They do not know history.
152 I don't mean like reciting every book, but they don't know how these major
153 political, geopolitical events affected society, how they affected the law,
154 what is the sense of justice. I might sound like a romantic, but if you are
155 in education, you see the outcome every day. A child at the age of 18
comes
156 into your classroom and they do not know the basics about being a human
and
157 a citizen of this world. When you start talking about the EU, they don't
158 even know how it was created, what it does, and how it affects every day.

..1.2. Social

..2.1. European

159 **FN:** What do you think, besides education, what would be the main tool you
160 would you do to change the way we negotiate about this at the moment?

..4.2. Civil Society & N

161 **EMK:** Well, civil engagement is definitely something that they need to
162 promote more by starting from education going forward. Like people, they
163 need to know why their voices are important. Showcase that their voices
164 actually matter in the formation of politics so that when negotiators go to
165 represent a certain position to express several interests, they do know
166 what the ones that they got represented want.

167 **FN:** To bring back the faith that was lost?

168 **EMK:** Yes.

169 **FN:** Thinking about especially about your time in politics, I feel like the
170 economics will not fit to this question too well, but if you remember back
171 about your most challenging negotiation that you took part in personally or
172 as a strategist.

173 **EMK:** I had a few, for different reasons. Do you want me to go to the
174 politics or extend it to the business?

175 **FN:** I'm super interested to be honest about both.

..3.1. Case Description

176 **EMK:** So, I'll start with the easiest of all. But it was tough. It was a
177 negotiation between Axiom Gris and another company in the US. It was for
a
178 trade agreement like imports and exports. We found it challenging because
179 of the cultural distance. It was when I haven't even thought about that
180 culture plays a role. So, it was let's say the kickstart of my research.
181 I've learned it the tough way. So, in Greece we are slow trusters. We do

..3.1.1. Challenges

182	not trust people easily. We believe that what the other person says it's a
183	lie and they want to frame you, trap you somewhere. this is the notion. So,
..3.1.1. Challenges	184 every professor that I had up to this point was talking to us like how to
185	negotiate and they said do not reveal your information, withhold it, do not
186	say the truth.
187	The Americans are completely opposite. So, at the time I was behaving the
..3.1.1. Challenges	188 way I was taught to behave and they got offended like Helen, don't you
189	trust us? And they were about to leave and I was like oh my God I just
190	messed up. No just sit down I will reveal my German culture. So mommy's
191	culture kicked in [Eleni's Mother lived in Germany for a long time] and I
192	said okay now we can talk like normal people. It feels so strange when you
193	are forced to negotiate a specific the way that the company has decided.
..3.1.1. Challenges	194 You know there was a panel upstairs a few minutes ago that it was about
195	the
196	negotiation as a strategy for the entire corporation so we constantly talk
197	about how important it is for businesses to have a strategy. But in this
198	case having a strategy was an obstacle. So, we went there and we did
199	exactly what the company taught us to do and what they wanted us, the
200	way
201	they wanted us to behave and we almost blew the negotiations up in the air.
202	So, it was quite challenging not to conclude but to shift the environment
203	because no trust was built. Actually, trust was ruined. To conclude this
204	deal after a huge turnover trying to shift completely the page was a big,
205	big, big challenge.
206	In the end we maintained good relationships. At least they maintained good
..3.1.2. Outcome Deter	207 relationships with me. I don't know about my fellow teammates from the
208	particular negotiations. They accepted that it was a mistake. It was quite
209	frank at that point: straight ahead. And I said okay I'm sorry this is what
210	we were told to do. I gave it up. I shared with them the strategy of the
211	business. It was against all regulations from the business. It was against
212	everything that they had but I made the deal. And that was practically the
213	reason why I left business negotiations because the business owners do
214	not
215	actually know how things work in reality.
216	So, in politics it was all a challenge like from day one. Our agreement was
..3.1. Case Description	217 that I would be there for a year to get him started for a member of the
218	parliament and then he would roll on his own. Unfortunately, I've extended
219	this agreement by six whole months and I resigned on my own terms. I said
220	okay, I cannot do this no more because it was a challenge from the
221	beginning. I've made a favour to work for him. He asked me as a friend and
222	I wanted to help him despite our ideological differences. West and East
223	that much difference. But it was tough because all this problem that I
224	mentioned it's something good. I have heard them say that the legislation
225	came into the office like newly drafted. The committee was in two days.
..3.1.1. Challenges	226 Everything was perfect. Technically the output to the environment to the
227	Greek economy was great. And they were like: "no we cannot vote
228	something
229	given to us from this particular party." I said okay, do you want to
230	collaborate with them like do it together. No. They do not collaborate
231	unless it is to form a government.
232	In any other case like if it's not the power at stake they refrain from
233	collaboration even at the cost of social well-being. That's what I hate in

230 political negotiations. And it's challenging for people like you and me
231 that we are into this world that we have learned to promote mutual benefits
232 to promote collaboration and long-term relations like we can form an
233 agreement no matter how different we are. No matter how different are our
234 aspects and our life styles we can be people that if we were not here
235 outside of the negotiating table, we might hate each other but we can still
236 make an agreement and a good agreement for both that's not happening in
237 politics so it's a challenge it confronts everything you know as a good
238 negotiation practice

239 **FN:** Would you see that as a part of transparency as well?

240 **EMK:** For me transparency is not only for other people to know what you do
241 but you need to justify what you do if I go outside and say Eleni myself, I
242 am 34 years old I'm transparent about my age why am I transparent about my
243 age why do I need to say my age out loud? So, it's good to be transparent
244 for your economics and things like that but to be transparent about your
245 private life goes too deep and to go and say that for example we have
246 transparency laws about the annual income okay I fill in the form everybody
247 knows my annual income and where it came from more or less why should I
248 tell them exactly how I created this money if it was for all citizens I
249 would have understood it if you want to be transparent you need to be
250 transparent everywhere.

251 Otherwise create a committee with civil engagement like take people
252 randomly from offices from your country form a committee that they would
253 know each year the financials it's not practical I know it might be a
254 little ideal romantic but yeah or you might take the income you might have
255 something like everybody should know because there might be corruption
256 in
257 there but there are other aspects of transparency. I announced my decision
258 without giving the reason behind I gave this decision. This is completely
different than economic annual income stuff.

259 Let's say it's good that it is public but when they go and say like we will
260 adopt the euro for example. That was a huge question in Greece in the
261 previous decade. During the negotiations for the memoranda and there
262 were a
263 lot of people that they were saying we will leave the eurozone and others
264 said no we will remain in the European Union in the eurozone. Nobody no
265 political party actually justified their stance they were creating polls
266 and it was a mini civil war inside the country. There were families that
267 they stopped talking to each other because one voted yes and the other
268 voted no but in the end, I asked someone why are you going to vote yes
269 why
270 are you going to vote no? "Because the political party I support said no or
271 said yes." But why nobody could go to the public and be transparent like
we
272 want this because one, two, three. They just announced their decision
273 without justifying it. Is that transparent? For me it's not.

274 **FN:** This disconnection between - if we talk about the politics, the civil
275 society, academics, practitioners on the ground - if you see all these
different actors who are involved in these kind of negotiations or at least
are a crucial part of why the negotiation goes the way it does. How would

276 you bridge the gap between the academics, the civil society, and the
277 politicians?

278 **EMK:** You have to see the system under what it is. A system. What one
279 particle of that system does it influences all the others to actually be
280 aware of what are the boundaries of the system. This is what you need to
281 work on mostly the boundaries of the system. Where it starts and when it
282 begins. Who do you want engaged in this system? Are there any strategies
to
283 expand the system? If you want to expand you need to know the existing
284 boundaries. It is not quite happening. Nobody can actually map out the
285 boundaries of the system. They have so many different views and
286 perspectives of who is part of the system and who is not part of the system
287 that they do not collaborate the way we want.

288 We see here this conference is a magnificent exception but usually there
289 are scholars in economics, there are scholars in management, scholars in
290 law, scholars in politics but when it comes to negotiations there is no
291 scholar in negotiation unless they say so. There is not a single PhD out
292 there saying PhD in negotiations. They are in governance, politics,
293 political theory, business management. You don't get the system in hand
you
294 don't get the full picture.

295 **FN:** Is this what you mean by who is in the system and who is out?

296 **EMK:** How can you define the boundaries? So, if you want to bring everyone
297 together and allow for this exchange of information. The multiple actors
298 that they are in the system they need to know that they are in the system.
299 So, if I don't know if I'm accepted somewhere or not how can I be involved
300 in these discussions? That is why initiatives like this like this
301 conference and the European Negotiation Association is so good because it
302 creates somehow it draws the boundaries of the system. The boundaries
are
303 flexible. You have seen all these different types of people: scholars,
304 practitioners, researchers, students they are all part of the system but
305 they actually know that there is a system. They know who to address to
306 become part of the system and where to go to exchange thoughts. We
need
307 more initiatives like that.

308 **FN:** To have the people realize how big the system is and how to be
309 holistic?

310 **EMK:** Exactly, spread the word! If you do not know. how are you going to be
311 part of it? How are you going to be engaged?

312 **FN:** Thinking about knowing that you're a part of the system and the power
313 clashes that we have in Europe now and especially in the European Union,
314 which I would see as quite a broad system. What do you think is the
315 European distinctiveness in the way we negotiate with each other
especially
316 in the European Union?

317 **EMK:** I don't know if it's a good or a bad thing but we end up drafting
318 agreements of the common denominators. The least common denominator.

..4.3. Bridging Strateg

..2.1. European

..2.1. European

319 If you
320 see the agreements on sensitive issues, they are all really basic. There
321 are multiple agreements but they say we agree to discuss this in another
322 session. 2015 for example, immigration negotiations they were drafting it
was before the EU-Turkey deal for immigration. Through Europe they

..2.1. European

323 agreed
324 to disagree and they agreed that they will talk about it in six months. Is
325 that a meaningful agreement? But they went out and they said we have an
agreement

326 **FN:** To disagree and maybe talk about but later?

327 **EMK:** Yes, we agreed upon revisiting the same issue. We do not let it go. So,
328 when you have all these member states with all the complexity of the
329 negotiation because it's not only us going there. Okay, we have delegations
330 and before the Euro groups we have the Euro working groups and even
before

..2.1. European

331 that each member state has its own process. And then after the negotiation
332 if there is an agreement at the EU level then you can get it's not what you
333 have asked for, obviously. It might have changes so you need to come back
334 and renegotiate with the parliament, with the civil society, with the
335 voters. So, you take a step back. In the EU we tackle so many things, it
336 has gone ginormous [sic]. I will use that word it's gigantic and enormous
337 but even larger than all these. It's not only about soft issues. They are
338 hard issues. Now they're talking about arms, they rearm Europe so they're
339 going slowly again just tackling again the defence. The agenda is so wide,
340 that it reminds of a very large organization. Taking into consideration key
341 lessons learned from management: the larger an organization is, the less
342 impact it has. Because reaching a significant change is so hard, takes so
343 long and the slower it responds to any change. If you try to respond
344 quickly you will see differences.

..5.4. Lessons Learned

345 For example, they've responded quite quickly during the pandemic. I was
346 astonished about how quickly they reached an agreement but in order to
347 reach that agreement they end up having something quite flexible. Okay,
348 they agreed that they will negotiate the deal for vaccinations like as an
349 EU but not all countries have the same internal process of who gets the
350 vaccine to vaccinate if they are like voluntary on a voluntary basis or if
351 they were mandatory, if they will have lockdown. We've seen different
352 responses throughout Europe. In Greece we had a nine-month lockdown.
You

353 couldn't go out at all. In Denmark I have a friend in Copenhagen, they said
354 why don't we go out we just wear a mask? So, we've seen significant
355 differences when tackling an issue that it was kind of virgin. It was the
356 least common denominator. We agreed on one, two, three. It was the
357 exception of the rule of not making significant changes. In sustainability,
358 they negotiated without very opening the spectrum, opening the dialogue
to

359 everybody involved to create the CSRD the directive for social
360 responsibility reporting. By the time it would have been here, the time I
361 believe in June, that it would start to be implemented actually a lot of
362 different actors within the system said: wait a minute we were in part in
363 these discussions. You see how everything connects. The systemic
approach.

364 They did not ask them to participate in the initial negotiations. The final

365 agreement was okay but had difficulties in the implementation phase. So,
366 they stepped in and they had what we call the omnibus initiative to change
367 the implementation after the agreement. Okay, there was an agreement.
There
368 were press releases and huge parties for the agreement. The negotiators
did
369 their job. they have final signatures on the paper but coming further
370 implementation phase where is the agreement? still on hold.

..2.1. European

371 **FN:** So, we have on the one side the search for the least common
denominator
372 and then at the same time the nation states really want to have their
373 flexibility on how to actually implement what is already the least common
374 denominator?

375 **EMK:** Yes, imagine that they put obstacles even in that. Even if it is the
376 most basic little incremental change. Imagine what would happen with the
377 radical change. There will be riots throughout Europe not only in my
378 country but in your country as well. In the entire south, north,
379 Scandinavia. I cannot imagine a single country in the European Union that
380 would not riot if a major radical change was actually put into force.

381 **FN:** What do you think would be the core competencies that are needed for
382 either our current negotiators or the next generation of negotiators?

383 **EMK:** Well, I don't know for our current negotiators. I cannot answer that
384 part. But I can definitely say that it's hard to teach old dogs new tricks.
385 People are reluctant to change and when you negotiate the same way, when
386 you work the same way for 30 years it's a little bit hard to follow new
387 trends and new rules. Unless you are really open minded but for the
younger
388 generation. I would start with teaching them how to be human.

..5.1. Essential Skills

389 **FN:** What does that mean?

390 **EMK:** We see that there is a lot of violence amongst youth. We see people
391 that they are young adults that they cannot actually identify their own
392 emotions yet handle them. we see people young people that they do not
have

..5.1. Essential Skills

393 basic respect for other people. These are the issues, these are core issues.
394 It's like they've lost part of what means to be human and live in an
395 organized society with laws and boundaries and responsibilities. So, if we
396 do not start from that basis, it's hard to talk about extra skills and
397 competencies because you need to foster a collaborative spirit. how can
you

..5.3. Teaching Methoc

398 teach someone to be collaborative when they only think about themselves
and
399 no one has ever told them that it's not only you walking on this earth.
400 There are other people as well that they have also rights and
401 responsibilities

402 **FN:** So, you would put the introspection as the first step to actually get
403 into a civic behaviour?

404 **EMK:** The way forward is to step a little backward because something is
405 missing throughout the history. I see that progressively like in the five

406 years that I was teaching undergraduate students. The 18-year-old student
407 that I had five years ago knew more and was more prone to have an open
mind
408 than the 18-year-old student that I had this semester.

..5.1. Essential Skills

409 They might have different digital skills but it's the only skill that they
410 show. They cannot form an argument. I don't see full engagement. They are
411 all opinionated, Gen Z is opinionated and quite aware of problems around
412 them. But when it comes for them to put the theory into practice, they
413 don't take it step by step. They just want to rush in like a know-it-all.
414 "I've read one book about this I know how to do it." So, to be patient and
415 to actually build on solid ground this is what we need to teach them so
416 that we can work on all the other competencies above that.

417 **FN:** Interesting perspective.

418 **EMK:** I have quite a different perspective I believe from a lot of people. I
419 don't know you might need to write this down that I'm on the autistic
420 spectrum, no kidding. About the high-factional autistic side of the
421 spectrum. I have a unique view on things.

422 **FN:** Taking these competencies and skills that we talked about, what would
423 you say is at the moment one of the most pressing research questions that
424 we have to ask in the field of negotiation? What do we need to research
425 what do we need to find out?

..6.1. Research Questic

426 **EMK:** Well, for personal reasons only, I would say culture. Let's start with
427 there is been a lot of research already done in the field. We have mapped
428 out a lot of things and for everyone that wants to get a hold of anything
429 related to negotiations there is certainly something written about it. For
430 me it is the time to take the theory and focus more into the practice. I
431 don't see a lot of practical research out there like with statistics
432 research to get statistically significant results. They are all talking
433 about theoretical frameworks and expanding but the practical side is a
434 little bit behind. This is one pillar the second pillar comes to the new
435 world as I say it. Yes, we have a lot of research already done but it
436 reflects a world that no longer exists. So, some of the theories that they
437 have been discarded they might be more appropriate to use in today's
world.

..6.1. Research Questic

438 Revisiting old frameworks and combining them with today's frameworks
might
439 give us more innovative perspectives over things. There was this trend to
440 discard older frameworks like something that it was created in the 1960s.
441 You don't even read it anymore. They say it's outdated and there are a lot
442 of professors that say to their students: "Do not use outdated materials."
443 It's something that we all heard but if you want to be called a scholar an
444 academic you need to know these frameworks.

445 How many innovative ideas were discarded in the previous years because
they
446 were too ambitious or too different or too innovative? That cannot be
447 implemented in practice and we later see after three, four, five decades
448 that they become relevant. The same history for negotiation theory
449 something that it was written in the previous century might actually have a
450 point in this century. Back then the person wrote this theory might have
451 been the laughingstock of the entire academic community but they are part

452 they need to be heard. To summarize the first pillar is about getting from
453 theory to practice but at the same time, the second pillar revisiting
454 theories try to find the missing brick because something is missing
455 definitely.

456 **FN:** So, to get the whole knowledge and revisit what we know already and
457 then see how we can actually put it into practice?

458 **EMK:** This is true for every single learning path. You cannot get advanced
459 calculus if you do not have the solid basis. You cannot build upon new
460 competencies if you don't have a solid foundation about what it means to
461 be
462 part of a society. That way you cannot invent or create innovative work,
unless you have studied a little bit of the past just to get a notion.

463 **FN:** This is the perfect pathway to my last question. I say the most
464 difficult. If you could recommend one piece of media, a song, a movie, a
465 book, whatever you would like in the field of negotiation to really
466 understand a piece. What would you recommend?

467 **EMK:** The very first book that actually shook my world was the Multilateral
468 Negotiation by William Zarkman. It's the Bible for diplomacy. Also, the
469 Diplomatic Negotiation by Paul Meerts. These are the two books that i
470 actually read as a person. I read those for pleasure, like at the beach. It
471 was nice to read about but something that a lot of people might find
472 interesting it's called The Culture Map by Erin Meyer. It's a book that it
473 is written by her perspective. Erin Mayer was a trainer for businesses she
474 trained the expatriates, like a business in France sending someone to
475 represent the business or to work at a different branch in another country.
476 In the Philippines for example and they went to her to talk, to her to
477 learn like to teach them pieces of the culture that they will find that
478 it's different from the one that they were living in. So, she collected
479 every piece of practical information from all these trainings that she did
480 and put everything in a book but it is not academic. You can read it and
481 actually get to know the theory behind she makes some referrals here and
482 there to theory but it is a light reading. You actually enjoy reading about
483 all these experiences in trainings, stories not only from negotiations like
484 purchasing per se but also how to negotiate with colleagues or HR
485 evaluation techniques which is an internal type of negotiation like you do
486 negotiate every day with your colleagues. It gives a perspective so
487 interesting that you understand that what is normal for you might not be
488 the normal for another person. It's fun to read I believe that people that
489 have read it, they all said to me like it's a great book to read so I'm
490 proposing it.